

ESTIMATION OF CHLORIDES IN OIL-WELL DRILLING MUDS*

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The estimation by potentiometric titration of chlorine-ion concentration which has certain practical applications of importance, has been studied from the viewpoints of accuracy and reproducibility. One hundred estimations each were made of the salinity of a number of normal drilling muds whose salinities were known. The arithmetic mean of each one hundred estimations agreed closely with the calculated chloride concentrations, the maximum variation being within 0.8%. The standard deviation from the arithmetic mean did not exceed 0.72% while the most probable value (obtained graphically) corresponded within 0.1% with the arithmetic mean.

Measurement of the chlorine ion concentration of drilling muds by titration of the pressure filtrate or centrifugate with standard silver nitrate solution, using potassium chromate as indicator, was found to give results on the average 13.6% lower than the calculated values. It is thought that this may be due to the adsorption of chlorine ion on the clay particles as a result of which some of the chlorine ions present in the mud do not pass into the pressure filtrate or centrifugate.

A series of samples from two drilling wells was analysed to find if variations in the chloride content would indicate reliably when and at what depth a watersand was penetrated. Results for one well are compared with estimations of salinity of cuttings removed from the drilling mud. Variations are more distinct in the case of the results for cuttings but the two curves obtained show points of resemblance and it is concluded that if the salinity of the watersand be high enough it can be reliably detected by continuous sampling of both the ingoing and outcoming mud and estimation of the chloride content by potentiometric titration.

The reproducibility of the potentiometric titration method using silver-silver chloride electrode for the quantitative estimation of chlorides in electrolytic solutions is well known (Kolthoff and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations", John Wiley and Sons N. Y. 1931). This method has also been used for estimating chloride content of soils (Wright "Soil Analysis", Thomas Murray & Co. London, 1943, 1st Ed., pp. 182-185.) In the estimation of the salinity of muds such as are used in oil-wells the degree of reproducibility obtainable is less certain and further, there are several sources of error, e.g., poisoning of the electrode, adsorption of chlorine ion by clay particles etc. which must be guarded against. The adsorption of chlorine ion by clay particles is reduced by carrying out the titrations at a sufficiently low p_H (Snyder, *Soil. Sci.*, 1933, 35, 43). To what extent, if at all, electrode poisoning by any particular drilling mud takes place can be ascertained only by actual titration of the mud to which known quantities of some chloride have been added. Such measurements have been made with five different samples of oil-well drilling muds.

The superiority of the electrometric method over volumetric methods for estimating chlorine ion concentration of electrolytic solutions appears well established, but its validity remains to be demonstrated in the case of muds or soil suspensions. Investigations on this topic have been carried out using both the filtrate obtained from the mud under pressure and the centrifugate in a series of volumetric titrations. The indicator used was potassium chromate. Samples of mud returns from two wells, and cuttings removed from the mud in one of these were examined for chloride to determine if watersands encountered in drilling could be detected by salinity changes in the drilling mud, by examination of cuttings, or by both.

EXPERIMENTAL

Muds.—Five different samples of mud were used, characteristics of which are indicated in Table I. The first was a mixture of raw clay and water and the second a mud of

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similar composition which had been treated with chemicals to improve its properties. The third was typical of well-matured drilling mud, while the fourth was a mud which had suffered contamination in several respects in course of use. The fifth was a sample of a typical drilling mud taken at a well.

TABLE I
Characteristics of mud used

No.	Method of preparation.	solids%.	p_H .	Initial salinity (parts/100,000).
1	Raw clay + water	33.7	7.22	5.5
2	Raw clay + water with subsequent chemical treatment	33.8	7.96	12.3
3	Reconditioned field mud	19.9	10.12	9.3
4	Well mud returns (unreconditioned)	35.5	9.71	20.0
5	Typical well mud	22.8	9.20	1.5

Reagents and Apparatus.—The strength of the pure silver nitrate solution used for titration was 0.00854*N*. The same silver nitrate solution was used for both volumetric and potentiometric titrations.

The apparatus for potentiometric measurements was more or less the same as that used by R. J. Best (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1929, 19, 533) for analysis of soils. A silver-silver chloride electrode was connected by means of a saturated potassium nitrate bridge containing 3% agar agar with a quinhydrone electrode, consisting of a platinum foil dipped in a buffer solution of p_H 3.0. The silver-silver chloride electrode was immersed in the mud which was titrated with a 0.00854*N* silver nitrate solution, until the direction of the current as indicated by a pointer galvanometer (1 scale division = 10^{-7} amp.) was just reversed. The galvanometer connected the two half-cells through a tapping key. The reversal of the current took place within 0.05 c.c. of the silver nitrate solution.

The silver-silver chloride electrode was prepared by sealing a piece of silver wire 1 mm. in diameter into a piece of glass tubing. The wire was coated over a length of about 3 cm. with silver chloride by making it the anode in the electrolysis of *N*/10-sodium chloride solution.

The quinhydrone electrode was prepared by adding 0.05 g. of quinhydrone to 12 c.c. of buffer solution of p_H 3.0 in a small beaker of 25 c.c. capacity.

Method.—The mud (5 c.c.) was diluted to 50 c.c. with distilled water in a 100 c.c. beaker and made acidic with sulphuric acid till the p_H was about 2.0. The silver-silver chloride electrode and the agar-bridge reached nearly to the bottom of the beaker and the suspension was stirred from time to time with a glass rod. The titration was continued until the galvanometer deflection was just reversed. About fifteen minutes were required for each electrometric titration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Known volumes of mud No. 3 were treated with various quantities of normal sodium chloride solution and the chloride content of each sample separately estimated by the electrometric method. The results are shown in Table II. The maximum deviation of observed salinity from the calculated value did not exceed 2% and the average deviation was -0.44%.

Thus the electrometric method is liable to give results 0.44% too low. This deviation is probably due to slight adsorption or blanketing of chlorine ion by clay particles of the gel. The difference is, however, within the range of experimental error.

In order to test the reproducibility of this method several mud samples of known salinity were prepared from all the five mud samples mentioned in Table I. One hundred separate salinity estimations were made with each sample prepared from muds Nos. 1, 2, 4 and 5. Some of the results are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The curves shown in Figs. 1 and 2 are symmetrical, resembling the normal curve of error. The most probable values in all cases closely agree with the arithmetic means. This will be clear from Table III where the standard deviations of the arithmetic means and the estimated errors of the standard deviations have been tabulated.

TABLE II

Electrometric Titration of Mud No. 3 treated with various quantities of Sodium Chloride.

Sodium chloride (N) added to 500 c.c. of mud.	Salinity calc. (Parts/100,000).	Salinity obs. (Parts/100,000).	Deviation of salinity obs. from calc. value.	Sodium chloride (N) added to 500 c.c. of mud.	Salinity calc. (Parts/100,000).	Salinity obs. (Parts/100,000).	Deviation of salinity obs. from calc. value.	Sodium chloride (N) added to 500 c.c. of mud.	Salinity calc. (Parts/100,000).	Salinity obs. (Parts/100,000).	Deviation of salinity obs. from calc. value.
Nil	9'30	9'30	0'00%	7 c.c.	91'13	90'50	-0'69	14 c.c.	172'96	172'00	-0'56
1 c.c.	21'29	21'30	+0'05	8	102'82	102'00	-0'79	15	184'65	184'50	-0'08
2	32'68	32'60	-0'24	9	114'51	114'00	-0'44	16	196'34	197'00	+0'34
3	44'37	44'00	-0'83	10	126'20	124'50	-1'35	17	208'03	206'50	-0'74
4	56'06	57'00	+1'68	11	137'89	136'50	-1'01	18	219'72	219'70	-0'01
5	67'75	66'90	-1'25	12	149'58	147'50	-1'39	19	231'41	230'72	-0'30
6	79'49	79'00	-0'62	13	161'27	160'50	-0'48	Average deviation—0'435%			

TABLE III

Comparison of calculated and experimentally determined salinities.

Salinity obs. (Parts/100,000)					Salinity obs. (Parts/100,000)						
Mud No.	Salinity calc. (Parts/100,000)	Arithmetic mean of 100 observations.	Most probable value.	Standard deviation of A. M.	Estimated error of standard deviation.	Mud No.	Salinity calc. (Parts/100,000).	Arithmetic mean of 100 observation.	Most probable value.	Standard devia. tion of A. M.	Estimated error of standard de. viation.
1	99'02	98'93	98'90	0'551%	0'0551%	4	101'83	101'07	101'20	0'719	0'0719
"	153'56	152'62	152'60	0'316	0'0316	"	148'58	148'14	148'10	0'383	0'0383
"	248'65	247'98	247'95	0'157	0'0157	"	253'80	252'71	252'80	0'195	0'0195
"	105'82	105'00	105'00	0'539	0'0539	5	101'50	101'87	101'85	0'473	0'0473
"	152'58	152'12	152'10	0'258	0'0258	"	155'47	155'36	155'30	0'425	0'0425
"	246'10	245'73	245'70	0'211	0'0211	"	235'30	235'33	235'30	0'275	0'0275
3	196'34	196'64	—	0'316	0'070*						

* Mean of 20 observations only.

It is evident from Table III that as the salinity of the mud increases the standard deviation of the arithmetic mean diminishes. With systems having very low salinity the reproducibility would be correspondingly less.

A comparative study of the electrometric and volumetric methods is given in Table IV. The average percentage error of the electrometric method is only +0'37% while that of the volumetric method is -13'35% in one case and -13'60% in the other. In the volumetric methods the filtrate from the mud and not the mud itself, has to be titrated and the lower results obtained by this method seem to be due to the fact that all the chlorine ions present in a mud do not appear in the centrifugate or filtrate obtained under pressure. Results obtained by potentiometric titrations of the filtrates corresponded within the limits of experimental accuracy with those of volumetric measurements.

TABLE IV

Comparison of the electrometric and the volumetric methods of salinity estimation.

(Mud from a typical drilling well—Well A)

Sodium chloride (N) per 500 c.c. of mud Nil c. c.	Salinity observed—(Parts/100,000)						
	Salinity calc. (Parts/100,000).	Electrometric method		Volumetric method		Centrifugate	
		Salinity.	Deviation.	Salinity.	Deviation.		Salinity.
1	18'89	19'00	+0'58	16'03	-15'14	15'70	-16'89
2	30'58	30'20	-1'24	30'45	-0'42	28'20	-7'78
3	42'27	43'30	+2'44	33'60	-20'51	34'60	-18'15
4	53'96	54'80	+1'56	44'05	-18'37	44'55	-17'44
5	73'25	73'70	+0'61	65'85	-10'10	64'50	-11'95
6	84'94	84'10	-0'99	73'25	-13'76	77'55	-8'70
7	96'63	96'80	+0'18	81'40	-15'24	84'45	-12'60
8	108'32	109'00	+0'63	92'25	-14'84	90'70	-16'27
9	120'01	120'70	+0'57	104'30	-13'09	97'25	-18'96
10	131'70	131'30	-0'30	112'95	-14'24	106'90	-18'83
	Average deviation		+0'367%		-13'35%		-13'60

TABLE V
Mud samples from Well A

Well depth	Pn	Conductivity.		Salinity (Parts/100,000)	
		(mho).	(Ag-AgCl Electrometric).	Pressure filtrate.	Centrifugate.
3645 ft.	9'41	0'835 × 10 ⁻³	12'5	11'3	11'3
3600	9'30	0'385	11'5	11'1	11'1
3720	9'41	0'788	12'0	11'3	11'3
3750	9'11	0'794	13'5	12'2	11'4
(Reaming)					
3750	9'31	0'820	16'5	12'5	13'4
(Reaming)					
3767	9'40	0'804	11'5	10'4	9'6
3773-81	9'35	0'788	15'0	12'9	11'3
Not recorded	9'10	0'788	10'5	8'7	7'9
3829	9'15	0'788	10'5	9'2	7'7
3884	9'46	1'056	9'5	9'25	9'2
3884	9'40	1'00	10'5	8'45	9'2
3890	9'45	0'91	10'0	8'95	9'8
(Reaming)					
3884-90	9'30	0'851	10'0	8'85	9'35
3900	9'50	0'82	9'5	9'10	9'9
3914	9'60	0'82	9'5	8'3	8'3
(Reaming)					
3916	9'60	0'898	9'0	7'35	8'35
3916-24	9'60	0'898	9'5	8'1	8'1
Not recorded	9'55	0'898	10'0	8'85	8'05
3962	9'45	0'791	12'0	12'10	11'3
4005-09	9'35	0'788	10'5	8'25	9'6
Not recorded	9'40	0'788	9'5	8'25	8'05
4039-42	9'45	0'791	8'5	7'20	8'0
4059-09	9'35	0'756	9'0	8'75	9'55
Not recorded	9'40	0'741	8'5	7'20	8'0
4082-02	9'35	0'725	8'5	7'80	7'80
4220-25	9'40	0'741	9'0	8'0	8'0
Not recorded	9'40	0'725	8'0	6'2	7'6
Not recorded	9'35	0'756	7'0	6'3	7'85
4301-16	9'30	0'788	9'5	8'8	8'0
—	9'30	0'772	8'0	8'10	6'45
4321-25	9'30	0'722	7'5	7'20	6'40
4341-46	9'50	0'704	8'0	8'15	8'15
4361-71	9'50	0'526	7'0	6'15	6'45
Not recorded	9'45	0'530	7'0	6'3	6'3
4325-39	9'35	0'708	8'2	7'05	8'15
(Reaming)					
Not recorded	9'25	0'824	7'1	6'15	6'80
4326-39	9'40	0'775	6'7	8'20	8'22
(Reaming)					
4439	9'45	0'791	7'2	8'20	6'57
(Reaming)					
4436	9'30	0'935	7'0	6'36	6'37
4439-41	9'20	—	8'0	8'0	7'80
4443	9'35	—	7'5	7'42	7'0
4470	9'40	—	7'5	8'0	7'60
4488-08	9'35	0'859	6'5	6'5	6'5
4510	9'25	0'859	6'3	5'8	5'95
4511-16	9'40	0'826	7'4	6'4	7'35
4560	9'35	0'866	9'4	7'6	8'55

TABLE VII
Mud samples from Well B

Salinity Depth ft.	(Parts / 100,000)	Salinity obs. by Ag-AgCl (Electrometric Method).		Salinity Depth ft.	(Parts / 100,000)	Salinity Depth ft.	(Parts / 100,000).
		Salinity Depth ft.	(Parts / 100,000)				
3674	16'5	3820	15'0	4732	12'0	4864	7'0
3678	15'5	3824	15'0	4740-4744	12'0	4868	7'0
3682	15'0	4625	13'0	4744-4748	10'0	4872	6'5
3786	16'0	4629	14'5	4748-4752	9'5	4874	6'0
3790	15'0	4633	14'5	4752-4756	9'5	4883	7'5
3794	15'0	4637	12'5	4764	7'7	4887	7'0
3798	16'0	4643	14'5	4768	7'8	4891	7'0
3802	16'5	4647	13'3	4772	7'5	4895	6'5
3806	15'5	4651	13'2	4776	7'0	4898	6'2
3816	15'0	4655	14'2	4780	8'5		

A series of mud samples was taken at a succession of depths in well A when drilling was

FIG. 3
Salinity records of mud and cuttings (Well A).

in progress and cutting in the mud separated. The mud and cuttings were examined for Cl-content in order to find if there were any significant increases in Cl-concentration which would indicate that a watersand had been penetrated. A similar set of mud samples were taken in well B but the cuttings were not examined. Results of these tests are given in Tables V and VI and Fig. 3. The cuttings curve shows the better defined maxima and minima and a very general correlation exists between the two curves: for example points P and Q in the one curve appear to correspond to points P₁ and Q₁ in the other. Had

there been a water-sand in either well with water of relatively high chloride content it seems that it would have shown up in the salinity estimations.

CONCLUSIONS.

- (i) The electrometric method gives accurate and reproducible results in salinity determinations in drilling muds.
- (ii) The volumetric method is unsatisfactory for estimation of chlorides in drilling muds.
- (iii) When the salinity of water in a watersand is sufficiently high analysis of the mud returns in a well penetrating the sand should indicate accurately the point at which the sand is struck.

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